

Photo oxidative degradation of metanil yellow by photo-Fenton reagent

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Abstract : At normal laboratory temperature and atmospheric pressure, experiment on waste water containing metanil yellow by photo-Fenton process were conducted to examine the effect of operating variables like the concentration of ferric ion, concentration of metanil yellow, pH, hydrogen peroxide and light intensity on the reaction rate. Metanil yellow was completely oxidized and degraded into CO₂ and H₂O in this experiment. A mechanism for photochemical bleaching of metanil yellow by photo-Fenton's reaction has been processed.

Keywords : Photochemical degradation, photo-Fenton, metanil yellow, advance oxidation processes.

Introduction

The dyes, due to many uses, are toxic and carcinogenic in nature, but bleached dye solutions are non-toxic and harmless. Technology for treating hazardous and toxic wastes is undergoing a transformation on discharge limits. Metanil yellow has shown to promote tumor enhancing effects, cause testicular damage in gametogenic elements to arrest spermatogenesis in guinea pigs. Rats and mice, induced haematological changes, effect the DNA synthesis and case of allergic contact dermatitis. Use of conventional oxidation and active charcoal as an absorbent have served industry well for decades but now, it cannot meet the more stringent regulations, and as a consequence, innovative technologies such as the advanced oxidation processes (AOP) have emerged for the destruction of organic compounds¹. The active species hydroxyl radical, attacks and destroys the undesired compounds. By homogenous and heterogeneous processes these radicals can be produced.

The Fenton's reaction² produces hydroxyl radicals by interaction of H₂O₂ with ferrous salts.

The reaction is retarded in dark after complete conversion of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺. In recent times, it is found that illumination of the Fe²⁺ – Fe³⁺ – H₂O₂ system increases

the degradation rate of many organic substances e.g. TNT and RDX³, orange II dye, nitrophenols⁴ and *p*-chloroniline⁵. Photoreduction is the reason for this positive effect on the rate of degradation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ ions, which produces new $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals with H₂O₂ according to the following mechanism :

The direct photolysis of H₂O₂ also generates $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals.

Photochemical degradation of azo dyes, namely red MX-5B, reactive black-5 and orange-G using low iron concentration in Fenton and Fenton like systems was studied by Liou *et al.*⁶. Decolonization of the solution containing a common textile and leather dye, C.I. acid red 14 (AR14), at pH 3 using Fenton, UV/H₂O₂/O₂, UV/H₂O₂/Fe²⁺, UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺ and UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺/oxalate processes was done by Daneshvar and Khataee⁷. The influence of alizarin violet 3B dye on the Fenton reaction of organic compounds under visible irradiation ($\lambda > 450 \text{ nm}$) was examined by Ma *et al.*⁸. Dutta *et al.*⁹ also chemically oxidized the methylene blue using Fenton like reaction. Prousek *et al.*¹⁰ reported the utilization of Fenton reaction for the degradation of dyes present in coloured waste water. Photodegradation of malachite green in the pres-

ence of $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ under visible irradiation has been observed by Wu *et al.*¹¹. The photo-Fenton reaction as an effective photochemical process to treat the polluted water was studied by Ruppert *et al.*¹². The photochemical degradation of *p*-dichlorobenzene and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid by photo-Fenton's reagent was reported by Mogra *et al.*^{13,14}. Intermediates in the reaction of Fenton's type reagents was studied by Walling¹⁵. Now, it is to show the photochemical degradation of metanil yellow by photo-Fenton's reagent using visible range of light.

Materials and methods :

In this investigation metanil yellow (Sisco), FeCl_3 (CDH) and H_2O_2 (30%, Merck) were used. In doubly distilled water the dye solution of metanil yellow was prepared. The photochemical degradation of metanil yellow was studied in the presence of Fe^{3+} ion, H_2O_2 and visible light 0.0375 g of metanil yellow was dissolved in the 100 ml of doubly distilled water ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and 0.4055 g of FeCl_3 anhydrous was dissolved in 500 ml of doubly distilled water so that the concentration of FeCl_3 solution was $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. These were used as stock solutions. The photochemical degradation of metanil yellow was observed taking 30 ml of dye solution ($2.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$) and 2.0 ml of FeCl_3 solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$). The reaction mixture was exposed to light (intensity 80.0 mW cm^{-2}). A tungsten lamp (200 W) was used for irradiation. For higher intensities of light Sunlight was used.

The intensity of light was measured by Suryamapi (CEL Model SM 201). Water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations. The pH of the solution was measured by a digital pH meter (Systronics Model 106). The desired pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of previously standardized hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions. The necessary conditions for the correct measurement of optical density is that the solution must be free from suspension and therefore centrifuge machine (Remi-1258) and Whatmann filter paper was used to remove the suspension but both were found suitable. Thus, G-3 sintered glass crucible was used for filtration to obtain the desired accuracy in measurement of optical density at different time intervals, whereas λ_{max} of the dye was determined with the help of ultraviolet-visible recording spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV 240).

Results and discussion

The photochemical degradation of metanil yellow was observed at λ_{max} 557 nm. The results for a typical run are given in Fig. 1. Optical density of metanil yellow solution was found decreasing with the increase in the time of irradiation; indicating that metanil yellow is consumed on irradiation. A plot of $1 + \log \text{OD}$ against time was linear and it followed pseudo-first order kinetics. The optimum rate constant k for this reaction was determined to be $9.60 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The spectral changes for these reactions have been shown in Fig. 2.

Fig 1. Variation of optical density with time.

Fig. 2. Spectral change for photo-Fenton reaction.

The photochemical degradation depends strongly on the pH of the reaction medium as it is evident from the data in Table 1 that the rate OH photochemical degradation of metanil yellow increases with increase in pH upto 1.6 and then the rate of reaction decreases with increasing pH. The hydroxyl radicals are generated by two steps : (i) The reaction between ferrous ions with hydrogen peroxide. (ii) Photochemical reaction of ferric ions and water. The increase in the pH of the medium favours the step, (i) where OH^- ions are formed along with hydroxyl radicals, whereas protons are generated in step (ii), thus it may be concluded that the step (i) dominates over step (ii) in the pH range below 1.6. However, retardation of the reaction above pH 1.6 suggests the dominance of step (ii) over step (i).

Table 1. Effect of pH

[Metanil yellow] = $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, H_2O_2 = 1.5 ml, Light intensity = 80.0 mW cm^{-2} , $[\text{Fe}^{3+}] = 1.60 \times 10^{-4} M$

pH	$K \times 10^4 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
1.3	6.98
1.4	7.35
1.5	8.53
1.6	9.60
1.7	8.35
1.8	6.40

The rate of photochemical degradation was found to increase with increasing concentration of metanil yellow upto $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$. On further increasing its concentration, a sudden decrease in the rate of degradation was

observed and this was presented in Table 2. This may be explained as, on increasing the concentration of metanil yellow, more molecules of metanil yellow are available for degradation. However, on increasing the concentration above $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, the reaction rate was found to decrease. It may be attributed to the fact that as the concentration of the metanil yellow was increased, it may start acting like a filter for the incident light, where its larger concentration will not permit the desired light intensity to reach the dye molecule in the bulk of the solution and thus, decrease in the rate of photochemical bleaching of metanil yellow was observed.

Table 2. Effect of metanil yellow concentration

pH = 1.6, $[\text{Fe}^{3+}] = 1.60 \times 10^{-4} M$, H_2O_2 = 1.5 ml, Light intensity = 80.0 mW cm^{-2}

[Metanil yellow] $\times 10^{-5} M$	$K \times 10^4 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
1.0	1.71
1.2	2.31
1.4	3.22
1.6	3.83
1.8	4.54
2.0	5.12
4.0	4.72
6.0	4.39
8.0	3.79
10.0	2.79
12.0	1.36
14.0	1.00
16.0	1.05
18.0	0.97

From the data given in Table 3, it is clear that the rate of photodegradation increases on increasing the concentration of Fe^{3+} ions upto $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, while a reverse trend was observed beyond this limit. This may be explained as, on increasing Fe^{3+} ions in the reaction mixture, the concentration of Fe^{2+} ions also increases, which is accompanied by enhanced generation of the active species $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals. As a consequence, the rate of photodegradation also increases. However, on increasing the concentration of Fe^{3+} ions further, the rate of the reaction was found to decrease due to the fact that Fe^{3+} ions imparts a yellow colour to the solution and at larger concentrations, it may also act as a filter for the incident light. As the concentration of Fe^{3+} was increased above its optimum concentration, the rate of the reactions (5)

Table 3. Effect of ferric ion concentration

[Metanil yellow] = $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, $H_2O_2 = 1.5$ ml, pH = 1.6,
Light intensity = 80.0 mW cm^{-2}

$[Fe^{3+}] \times 10^5 M$	$K \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$
1.0	3.83
1.2	4.79
1.4	4.86
1.6	4.94
1.8	5.14
2.0	5.45
2.2	8.06
2.4	9.60
2.6	6.91
2.8	4.61
3.0	4.48

and (6) become very fast. Now, in reaction (5), hydroperoxyl radicals ($\bullet OOH$) are generated, which consumed more amounts of Fe^{3+} ions and hence, Fe^{3+} ions are less for reaction (4) and as a consequence less $\bullet OH$ radicals are generated and the rate of photodegradation also decreases.

In Table 4, it was observed that the rate of reaction increases on increasing the amount of $H_2O_2 = 1.5$ ml. Thereafter, the rate of degradation decreases on increasing the amount of hydrogen peroxide above 1.5 ml. This

Table 4. Effect of hydrogen peroxide

[Metanil yellow] = $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Fe^{3+}] = 4.0 \times 10^5 M$, pH = 1.6, Light intensity = 80.0 mW cm^{-2}

H_2O_2 (ml)	$K \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$
0.5	7.85
1.0	8.72
1.5	9.60
2.0	8.53
2.5	8.40

may be explained as that, more H_2O_2 molecules are available for Fe^{2+} ions to react, which increases the number of $\bullet OH$ radicals. On further increasing the amount of H_2O_2 more than 1.5 ml, the rate of reaction was found to decrease. It is due to the fact that as the amount of H_2O_2 increased above its optimum value (1.5 ml) the rates of

reactions (7) and (8) become fast. From reaction (8) $\bullet OH$ radicals are consumed rapidly due to more H_2O_2 molecules. From reactions (7) and (8) $\bullet OOH$ radicals increase and are utilized in reaction (9) where H^+ ions is confirmed by a slight decrease in pH of the reaction mixture at the end of reaction. As a consequence, the rate of photodegradation decreases.

A linear plot was observed between the rate constant and light intensity, which indicates that an increase in the light intensity increases the rate of reaction. This may be attributed to the increased number of photons reacting with Fe^{3+} ions and as a result, there is an increase in the number of active species, the hydroxyl radicals and corresponding increase in the rate of reaction (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of light intensity

[Metanil yellow] = $2.4 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Fe^{3+}] = 4.0 \times 10^5 M$, pH = 1.6, $H_2O_2 = 1.5$ ml

Light intensity (mW cm^{-2})	$K \times 10^4 (s^{-1})$
10.0	6.01
20.0	6.95
30.0	7.99
40.0	8.39
50.0	8.60
60.0	8.95
70.0	9.32
80.0	9.60

Mechanism :

On the basis of experimental observations and corroborating the existing literature, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for photodegradation of metanil yellow with photo-Fenton reagent.

The aqueous solutions of ferric ions on exposure to light dissociate water into a proton and $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical and ferric ions are reduced to ferrous ions. These ferrous ions will decompose H_2O_2 into hydroxyl ion and hydroxyl radical, while ferrous ions undergo oxidation to ferric ions. The ferric ions generate $\bullet\text{OOH}$ radical due to dissociation of H_2O_2 in presence of light. The incorporation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ with H_2O_2 also produces $\bullet\text{OOH}$ radicals. Ferrous ions will undergo oxidation to ferric ions by addition of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals, while ferric ions get reduce to ferrous ions by incorporation of $\bullet\text{OOH}$ radical and producing H^+ ions. $\bullet\text{OOH}$ radicals are highly unstable in water and undergo facile disproportion rather than reacting slowly with dye molecules. The participation of hydroxyl radicals as an active oxidizing species likes 2-prepanol, where the rate of photodegradation was drastically reduced. There are two possibilities for the consumption of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals namely (a) hydroxyl radicals may dissociate H_2O_2 into $\bullet\text{OOH}$ and water or combine together to form H_2O_2 molecules, (b) it may react with metanil yellow to give the colorless degradation products. This is important from an industrial point of view because further separation of ferric ions is not required after waste water treatment¹⁶⁻²¹.

The main advantage of using photo-Fenton's reagents is the regeneration of the consumed Fe^{2+} ions on illumination. Each Fe^{2+} ion can produce many $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals in contrast to the dark Fenton reaction. The process is a cyclic in nature, where only a single $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical is formed by one ferrous ion. It means that the amount of ferrous salt required under photo-Fenton conditions is very small as compared to Fenton conditions, where ferrous ions are to be added at regular intervals; otherwise, the reaction will stop after complete conversion of ferrous ions to ferric ions.

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